

Secure Federated Learning in Distributed Environments: A Blockchain-Based Approach

Eduardo Cánovas Martínez^{*†}, Jose Manuel Bernabe Murcia^{*†}, Liubov Nedoshivina[†],
Stefano Braghin[†], and Antonio Fernando Skarmeta Gomez^{*}

^{*}University of Murcia

Murcia, Spain

[†]IBM Research

Dublin, Ireland

Abstract—The adoption of publicly available AI models in real-world applications is often hindered by discrepancies between training datasets and real-world data, largely due to privacy, security, and business sensitivity constraints. While online training techniques enable models to adapt to specific use cases, they require a secure data-sharing mechanism to facilitate collaborative model updates across deployments. Existing cryptographic-based solutions introduce significant computational overhead, while data-masking techniques often degrade model performance.

This paper presents SFLDE, a novel blockchain-based mechanism for secure and private model updates in fully distributed systems. SFLDE follows Zero Trust principles, ensuring confidentiality and privacy protection during model aggregation. By leveraging blockchain and decentralized identifiers, our approach enables verifiable, trust-based model updates while maintaining plausible deniability for participating entities.

SFLDE is currently being integrated into the FLUIDOS MetaOS as the preferred mechanism for decentralized model sharing. This paper details the SFLDE architecture, discusses its security and scalability advantages, and outlines its planned implementation and evaluation in real-world distributed environments.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Blockchain, Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), Smart Contracts, Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning, Secure Model Aggregation, Distributed Hash Table (DHT), Zero Trust, Decentralized AI, Secure Data Sharing, Hyperledger Fabric.

I. INTRODUCTION

The utilization of openly released models in the real worlds is often prevented from models being trained on dataset not perfectly aligned with the data observed in practice. This is often the case because of open model being trained on publicly available dataset, which are often heavily redacted due to security, privacy, and business sensitivity concerns.

To foster adoption of the model, the usage of techniques for online training are strongly advised to adapt model behavior for specific use cases. This means that the model will be customized and perfected for one specific use case. In order to further augment the capabilities across deployments, a secure data-sharing mechanism for AI-based systems is needed. Traditionally, cryptographic-based systems [1] are used, with challenges from the computational – both time and space – point of view. Alternatively, techniques to mask the private information contained in the original data [2] are used, with performance degradation of the final resulting model.

Currently these approaches are limiting the adoption of such data and model sharing capabilities. In particular in those scenarios where computational resources are limited and where preservation of high models accuracy is paramount, such as on 6G enabled edge devices, or with battery-powered robotic devices.

We here present the Secure Federated Learning in Distributed Environments (SFLDE), a novel blockchain-based mechanism for secure and private model updates in a fully distributed system. This mechanism follows Zero Trust principles to allow confidentiality and privacy protection of the shared model updates. Thus, allowing entities to train model on potentially confidential information by allowing plausible deniability, as the aggregation processes are performed in an oblivious manner from the model user point of view.

The SFLDE approach is currently being adopted as the preferred mechanism for model sharing within the FLUIDOS MetaOS.¹

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the context and the techniques leveraged by our approach, which is thoroughly presented in Section III. Section IV compares relevant literature, and Section V summarizes the contribution and depicts future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND

A. The FLUIDOS Framework

This section provides an overview of the framework that serves as the foundational environment for our proposed security solution. FLUIDOS (Flexible, Scalable, Secure, and Decentralized Operating System) is a research initiative focused on creating a decentralized operating system. Its goal is to seamlessly integrate and manage distributed computing resources, allowing users to deploy services without worrying about the underlying infrastructure. By abstracting deployment complexities, FLUIDOS ensures that services meet predefined requirements while maintaining security. This system enables multiple independent providers to contribute and utilize resources across various nodes, fostering flexibility and adaptability for a wide range of applications. The FLUIDOS security approach is mentioned and explained in the solution

¹<https://fluidos.eu/>

for a Decentralised Identity Management solution for Zero-Trust Multi-domain Computing Continuum Frameworks [3].

B. Privacy and Security Manager

The Privacy and Security Manager is a main component of the FLUIDOS Architecture in charge of providing the security features related with Authentication/Authorization and Trust; it also provides a Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) Module that includes the functionality to the nodes of generating own identifiers, request Verifiable Credentials – for Attribute Based Access-control – from trusted entities of the decentralized architecture, generating Verifiable Presentations of those Verifiable Credentials to allow the authorization of the nodes in different processes, thanks to BBS Cryptography this Verifiable Presentations can hide attributes from the original Verifiable Credential in order to disclose only the attributes that we need for each authorization process. This component also includes the capability of Verify these credentials and presentations as well as it provides the possibility to sign documents/objects using the Private Key of a DID generating a signet JSON Web Token (JWT).

1) *Node trust and reputation manager*: This paper focuses on security and federated learning, particularly how trust management influences decentralized decision-making. The Trust and Reputation Manager ensures authorization through continuous evaluation, following Zero Trust Architecture principles. A crucial aspect is determining whether nodes should act based on their trust scores and ensuring that the models they contribute to the federated learning system maintain high quality. A higher trust score should correlate with better model contributions, improving the system's overall performance. Additionally, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) enhances trust management by providing verifiable and traceable exchanges.

2) *Decentralized Identifiers*: Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs)² are self-managed, globally unique identifiers that enable secure authentication without third-party control. They link a subject, such as a node, to a DID document containing cryptographic keys, verification methods, and services, ensuring secure interactions and identity ownership.

A DID consists of three main components:

- **DID URI Scheme** – The identifier starts with the prefix "did:", marking it as a Decentralized Identifier.
- **DID Method** – This part specifies the mechanism used to generate and manage the DID.
- **Method-Specific Identifier** – A unique value assigned within a specific DID method to differentiate individual DIDs.

An example of a DID is:

```
did:example:123456789abcdefghi
```

Breaking down this example:

- did: denotes the URI scheme, indicating it is a DID.

- `example` refers to the DID method, which defines the rules for its creation and resolution.
- `123456789abcdefghi` is the method-specific identifier that uniquely distinguishes this DID within the selected method.

This format complies with the URI scheme specifications as per [4], ensuring broad compatibility and interoperability in decentralized identity frameworks.

3) *Distributed Ledger Technology*: Distributed ledgers play a crucial role in authentication systems by serving as immutable and auditable registries for identity management and secure data exchange. The DLT component acts as a secure repository for identity-related information, such as public cryptographic keys and DIDs, allowing nodes to verify ownership and control of their identities. Additionally, DLT provides a transparent record of resource-sharing activities, tracking both successful exchanges and failed attempts. This ensures traceability and offers valuable insights into the interactions and collaboration dynamics within a distributed network.

4) *Functionality provided by the FLUIDOS framework*: DIDs and Verifiable Credentials (VCs) to enable secure, verifiable, and privacy-preserving interactions between nodes. These functionalities are exposed through an API based on the Hyperledger Aries Go implementation, which facilitates seamless identity management. Additionally, the API is connected to Hyperledger Fabric via a dedicated library, allowing interaction with the blockchain to trigger smart contracts for retrieving and storing DIDs.

A key feature of this framework is the use of ABC that combined with selective disclosure provided by BBS Signatures allow entities to prove specific attributes without revealing unnecessary information. To enhance security and ensure the authenticity of enrolled entities, FLUIDOS includes a mechanism where signed identity proofs are provided alongside credential requests. This ensures that the requesting entity truly possesses the claimed attributes before receiving a verifiable credential.

- **DID Self-Generation** Nodes can autonomously generate their own Decentralized Identifiers, ensuring identity sovereignty and privacy without reliance on centralized authorities.
- **Enrolment process (VCredential Request)** During enrollment, nodes request attribute-based Verifiable Credentials (ABCs) from a trusted issuer. To verify authenticity, the credential request must include a signed identity proof confirming that the entity genuinely possesses the claimed attributes.
- **Verifiable Presentation Generation** Nodes can generate Verifiable Presentations (VPs), selectively disclosing only the necessary attributes from their credentials. This enables privacy-preserving authentication while proving eligibility for certain services.
- **VCredential Verification** The system supports verification of attribute-based credentials, ensuring that they are valid, cryptographically secure, and issued by a trusted authority.

²<https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>

- **JWT DID-Signature** The FLUIDOS framework enables JWTs to be signed using DIDs, ensuring secure authentication and authorization. Additionally, it supports nested signatures and multiple signatures on the same document or object. This allows multiple entities to sign contracts, agreements, or transactions in a sequential or parallel manner, creating a verifiable chain of trust.
- **JWT Signature Verification** The framework can verify all signatures on a document, ensuring their validity and completeness before a contract or agreement is finalized.

C. FLUIDOS Distributed Learning System

Federated Learning (FL) [5] is a decentralized approach to machine learning that enables multiple devices or institutions to collaboratively train a shared model without exchanging raw data. Unlike traditional centralized learning, where data is aggregated and processed in a central server, federated learning allows model updates to be computed locally on each participant’s device or server. These updates, rather than the actual data, are then securely aggregated to improve the global model while preserving privacy. This approach is particularly beneficial in scenarios where data privacy is a concern, such as healthcare, finance, and mobile applications, as it reduces the risks associated with data sharing and centralized storage.

Traditionally, FL application rely on a trusted third party acting as aggregator. The confidentiality of the system relies on the fact that in a non byzantine scenario given a sufficient number of participants to the FL process, it is not feasible for an attacker to identify individual model contribution. Thus, it is not computationally feasible for an attacker to learn information about a specific participant.

In addition to that, the FLUIDOS distributed learning system leverages Differential Privacy (DP) techniques [2], [6], [7] to provide a formal guarantee about the privacy protection of the information the model learns from the locally available training data.

III. SECURE FEDERATED LEARNING IN DISTRIBUTED ENVIRONMENTS METHOD

The FLUIDOS framework introduces a decentralized approach to AI model sharing, ensuring security, traceability, and controlled access to sensitive data. This section outlines the primary challenges and architectural components involved in the management of model updates and aggregation.

A. Challenges in Secure Model Management

Two main challenges must be addressed:

- 1) **Controlled Access to the Distributed Hash Table (DHT):** The DHT stores both private model computations from individual nodes and public models from external repositories (e.g., Hugging Face, GitHub, Zenodo). If unrestricted access were allowed, it could lead to unauthorized exploitation of private models and sensitive deployment data.
- 2) **Trust and Security in Model Contributions:** Allowing nodes to push models to the DHT without traceability

could lead to the inclusion of malformed or malicious models, compromising system integrity.

In order to reduce these risks, every submitted model is linked to the **Decentralized Identifier (DID)** of the responsible node, ensuring accountability. Additionally, a trust scoring mechanism allows the system to penalize nodes that push low-quality or fraudulent models.

Furthermore, model aggregation—where individual models are combined to form improved versions—is securely executed. Each aggregation is recorded on the blockchain, providing a **transaction ID** and a complete trace of the models involved. This mechanism enables transparency and ensures that malicious models can be detected and discarded.

B. FLUIDOS Federated Learning Node Security Architecture

The security architecture for the Federated Learning approach of a **FLUIDOS Node**, Figure 1 consists of several interconnected components that ensure decentralized and secure model management.

a) *Model Treatment Gateway:* Acts as the primary interface for nodes to interact with the system, facilitating secure model submission and aggregation requests while enforcing validation rules.

b) *Smart Contracts for Model Management:* Two smart contracts ensure the secure handling of models:

- **Model Updates Smart Contract:**
 - Validates model updates, ensuring authenticity through **DID-Signed JWTs**.
 - Stores verified model updates in the **DHT** (private access).
 - Logs transactions in the **DLT** (public blockchain) with metadata, including node DID, timestamp, and transaction ID.
- **Model Aggregation Smart Contract:**
 - Retrieves models from the **DHT**—ensuring controlled access and preventing nodes from directly fetching private data.
 - Aggregates multiple models while verifying authenticity and trustworthiness.
 - Records aggregated models in the **DLT** for transparency and immutability.

c) *Distributed Hash Table (DHT) - Private Access:* The DHT serves as the secure storage system for private model updates. Access is strictly **restricted to smart contracts**, ensuring that nodes cannot retrieve models directly.

d) *Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) - Public Blockchain:* The DLT maintains an immutable record of model updates and aggregations, ensuring that all modifications are transparent and verifiable. Each transaction includes:

- A unique **Transaction ID** for traceability.
- A record of **all contributing models** in an aggregation.
- A reference to the **DID of the responsible node**.

Fig. 1. FLUIDOS FL Node Security Architecture

1) *Ensuring Security and Trustworthiness*: The integration of smart contracts, the DHT, and the DLT ensures a **trustworthy, decentralized, and auditable** model-sharing framework. The following mechanisms are enforced:

- **DID-based Authentication**: Every model update and aggregation is linked to a node’s DID.
- **Restricted Access to the DHT**: Only smart contracts can retrieve models from the DHT.
- **Blockchain Transparency**: The DLT ensures all transactions are verifiable and immutable.
- **Trust Score Mechanism**: Nodes pushing low-quality models may have their trust scores adjusted.

This architecture provides a **secure, decentralized, and verifiable AI model management system**, forming the foundation for the planned implementation detailed in the following section.

C. Model Treatment Gateway

To facilitate secure and traceable interactions within the FLUIDOS environment, a Model Treatment Gateway is proposed. This gateway will act as an intermediary between computing nodes and the blockchain infrastructure, enabling controlled model updates and aggregation through a REST API. It will ensure accountability, security, and verifiability by leveraging Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), cryptographic signatures, and smart contracts on Hyperledger Fabric [8].

- The gateway will be responsible for two main operations:
- **Model Updates** Nodes will be able to submit updates to existing models while ensuring authenticity and traceability through smart contracts.
 - **Model Aggregation** Multiple models will be combined into a new aggregated model, maintaining full trans-

parency of contributions and preventing direct manipulation of the DHT.

1) *Smart Contract: Model Updates*: To achieve these goals, the gateway will expose a set of API endpoints that interact with smart contracts deployed on the blockchain. These interactions will ensure that every update and aggregation follows a verifiable and structured process.

Model Updates The system will support the submission, retrieval, and querying of model updates. Each update request will require the following fields:

- **Base Model Identifier**: Specifies which model is being updated.
- **Version**: Identifies the version of the base model.
- **Timestamp**: Marks the submission date.
- **Node DID**: Links the update to the contributing node.
- **Signed Proof**: Provides a cryptographic signature ensuring authenticity.
- **Model Update Data**: Represents the model parameters being modified.

Additionally, querying mechanisms will allow retrieving updates by ID or date range, ensuring flexibility in accessing historical model modifications.

```

{
  "baseModel": "modelname1",
  "baseModelVersion": "version2",
  "date": "2024-03-01",
  "nodeDID": "did:example:123456789abcdefghi",
  "signedProof": "eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cGU6IjY9",
  "data": [
    [1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0],
    [5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0],
    [9.0, 10.0, 11.0, 12.0],
    [13.0, 14.0, 15.0, 16.0]
  ]
}

```

Listing 1. Model Update Creation Example

prior trust relationship. This approach leverages **Decentralized Identifiers** and **permissioned blockchains** to facilitate access control in multi-party IoT systems. A more general decentralized identity management solution is presented in [3], where the authors propose a **zero-trust multi-domain computing framework** that utilizes **Self-Sovereign Identity, Verifiable Credentials, and Distributed Ledger Technologies** to enhance authentication and authorization while preserving privacy.

Federated learning (FL) combined with blockchain has also gained significant attention. A comprehensive survey of blockchain-enabled FL is presented in [10], where the authors identify emerging challenges and promising research directions in this domain. Similarly, [11] investigates key issues in **FL-chain** design, including communication overhead, resource allocation, incentive mechanisms, and security/privacy challenges, particularly in edge computing environments.

The classification of blockchain-integrated federated learning architectures is discussed in [12], where the authors define three primary models—**decoupled, coupled, and overlapped**—based on the level of integration between FL and blockchain functionalities. These studies highlight the need for **privacy-preserving mechanisms**, incentive structures, and efficient model updates to improve decentralized learning systems. The work in [1] introduces **FedML-HE**, a homomorphic encryption-based privacy-preserving FL system that selectively encrypts sensitive parameters, significantly reducing computation and communication overhead while maintaining customizable privacy levels. Additionally, in [2], the authors examine **federated continual learning with differentially private data sharing**, addressing temporal shifts in client behavior and proposing data-sharing techniques to mitigate performance degradation in replay-based FL methods.

A more decentralized and privacy-preserving approach to multi-party machine learning is presented in [13], where the authors introduce **Biscotti**, a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) federated learning framework using blockchain and cryptographic techniques. Biscotti ensures secure model training while maintaining high performance, even when adversarial clients make up 30% of the network.

Other works have addressed the challenges of privacy and security in federated learning. The authors of [6] analyze **differential privacy-enhanced FL** and evaluate its impact on model performance. Their findings indicate a trade-off between privacy guarantees and learning accuracy. Additionally, the IBM differential privacy library, Diffprivlib, is introduced in [7], providing practical tools for implementing privacy-preserving federated learning.

These studies collectively emphasize the potential of integrating blockchain with federated learning for secure, scalable, and decentralized AI applications. However, they also highlight existing gaps in trust management, model aggregation efficiency, and privacy-enhancing mechanisms—issues that our work aims to address by leveraging Hyperledger Fabric, smart contracts, and a decentralized model-sharing approach.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a secure and decentralized framework for federated learning in distributed environments by integrating blockchain, smart contracts, and decentralized identifiers. Our approach ensures controlled access to the Distributed Hash Table, enforces trust-based model aggregation, and maintains transparency and accountability through blockchain-based logging. As future work, we will focus on the implementation of the proposed framework, conducting extensive scalability testing with performance evaluations and experimenting in real-world environments to assess the system's efficiency, security, and adaptability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research was supported by the EU FLUIDOS project, Grant Agreement No. 101070473, the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation, the European Union – nextGeneration EU [TSI-063000-2021-36, TSI-063000-2021-44, TSI-063000-2021-45, TSI-063000-2021-62]. It has been also partially funded by the European Union's Horizon Research & Innovation Action (RIA) programme under grant agreement No 101136024 (EMPYREAN) and it was partially funded by the HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-01 project Cloudstars (G.A. No. 101086248).

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Jin, Y. Yao, S. Han, J. Gu, C. Joe-Wong, S. Ravi, S. Avestimehr, and C. He, "Fedml-he: An efficient homomorphic-encryption-based privacy-preserving federated learning system," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.10837*, 2023.
- [2] G. Zizzo, A. Rawat, N. Holohan, and S. Tirupathi, "Federated continual learning with differentially private data sharing," in *Workshop on Federated Learning: Recent Advances and New Challenges (in Conjunction with NeurIPS 2022)*, 2022.
- [3] J. M. B. Murcia, E. Cánovas, J. García-Rodríguez, A. M. Zarca, and A. Skarmeta, "Decentralised identity management solution for zero-trust multi-domain computing continuum frameworks," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 162, p. 107479, 2025.
- [4] T. Berners-Lee, R. T. Fielding, and L. M. Masinter, "Uniform Resource Identifier (URI): Generic Syntax." RFC 3986, Jan. 2005.
- [5] C. Zhang, Y. Xie, H. Bai, B. Yu, W. Li, and Y. Gao, "A survey on federated learning," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 216, p. 106775, 2021.
- [6] K. Wei, J. Li, M. Ding, C. Ma, H. H. Yang, F. Farokhi, S. Jin, T. Q. Quek, and H. V. Poor, "Federated learning with differential privacy: Algorithms and performance analysis," *IEEE transactions on information forensics and security*, vol. 15, pp. 3454–3469, 2020.
- [7] N. Holohan, S. Braghin, P. Mac Aonghusa, and K. Levacher, "Diffprivlib: the ibm differential privacy library," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.02444*, 2019.
- [8] E. Androulaki, A. Barger, V. Bortnikov, C. Cachin, K. Christidis, A. De Caro, D. Enyeart, C. Ferris, G. Laventman, Y. Manevich, *et al.*, "Hyperledger fabric: a distributed operating system for permissioned blockchains," in *Proceedings of the thirteenth EuroSys conference*, pp. 1–15, 2018.
- [9] N. Fotiou, I. Pittaras, V. A. Siris, and G. C. Polyzos, "Enabling opportunistic users in multi-tenant iot systems using decentralized identifiers and permissioned blockchains," *Proceedings of the 2nd International ACM Workshop on Security and Privacy for the Internet-of-Things*, 2019.
- [10] Y. Qu, M. P. Uddin, C. Gan, Y. Xiang, L. Gao, and J. Yearwood, "Blockchain-enabled federated learning: A survey," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 1–35, 2022.

- [11] D. C. Nguyen, M. Ding, Q.-V. Pham, P. N. Pathirana, L. B. Le, A. Seneviratne, J. Li, D. Niyato, and H. V. Poor, "Federated learning meets blockchain in edge computing: Opportunities and challenges," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 16, pp. 12806–12825, 2021.
- [12] J. Zhu, J. Cao, D. Saxena, S. Jiang, and H. Ferradi, "Blockchain-empowered federated learning: Challenges, solutions, and future directions," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 55, no. 11, pp. 1–31, 2023.
- [13] M. Shayan, C. Fung, C. J. Yoon, and I. Beschastnikh, "Biscotti: A blockchain system for private and secure federated learning," *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 1513–1525, 2020.